

Speaking in tongues – Assessing user experience in a global economy

Gaël Laurans – Faculty of Industrial Design, Delft University of Technology, Landbergstraat 15, 2628 CE Delft, The Netherlands, +31 15 27 87 660, G.F.G.Laurans@tudelft.nl

Pieter Desmet – Faculty of Industrial Design, Delft University of Technology, Landbergstraat 15, 2628 CE Delft, The Netherlands, +31 15 27 83 375, P.M.A.Desmet@tudelft.nl

Abstract

After briefly highlighting some issues and questions in cross-cultural research about emotion, this article provides a review of some the tools available to measure feelings in different languages. The development of a Dutch translation of a new instrument, the Geneva Emotion Wheel (Scherer, 2005) is described with a study of its usefulness in a design context. Participants (N = 40) used two products and were asked to report about their feelings using the Geneva Emotion Wheel and PrEmo. (Desmet, 2003). Both measurement tools yielded similar results and were able to show differences in user experience between the products.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank Klaus Scherer and Johnny Fontaine for their help in translating the Geneva Emotion Wheel and Marleen Beuzekom and David Güiza Caicedo for their role in setting up and running the experiment presented here.

Conference theme: Design & Emotion, methodological issues

Keywords: culture, measurement, Geneva Emotion Wheel, PrEmo

Introduction

Design research and practice is often an international endeavor. Many products are sold all over the world or must be developed and adapted for several markets. Many researchers are also interested in cultural differences and commonalities in user experience. While qualitative approaches are often the method of choice to study cultural aspects of product use in depth, quantitative or experimental research can also be an important tool in this area, especially to compare how products are experienced by diverse people and to test models of user experience. In this context, measurement of emotion is a thorny problem, not least because it is mostly based on verbal descriptions of feelings, which can be particularly difficult to translate without losing much of the original nuances.

The extent and nature of cultural variations in emotion is a vexed question on which much has been written.

Research on this topic exists since a long time in several traditions, including anthropology (Lutz, & White, 1986), sociology or psychology. Depending on their disciplines and interest researchers resort to different methodologies from ethnography to survey research (Scherer, & Wallbott, 1994) and experimental (Ekman, & Oster, 1979), often with conflicting results. Another rough distinction, crossing disciplines and methodologies, can be made between “universalists”, stressing universals and commonalities in the structure of affective responses and “differentialists”, more interested in the nuances of emotional experience in specific groups or cultures. While these quick distinctions do not do justice to the wide range of research and theories in this area, they give an idea of the complexity of the issues at hand.

A useful way to articulate the various approaches is to think of them in terms of processes and contents. Processes are generally thought as the province of the psychologist, uncovering stable structures shared by all human beings while content, building upon the psychological structure to shape our particular experience of the world, is the main interest of sociologists and cultural anthropologists. Obviously, this division has been heavily criticized, for example by constructionists (for an example, see Mesquita, 2005) or cultural psychologists but it remains the dominant framework within affective science. From a design point of view, it is easy to conceive of different people feeling frustration or satisfaction with different products (say a car or an hair-dryer) depending on their concerns and values (Desmet, & Hekkert, 2002) and still expressing one or the other much in the same way, be it through spontaneous behavior, free verbalizations or formal self-report questionnaires.

Still, even accepting this broad division of labor leaves open the question of the extent and nature of the universal processes and hence of the range of contents and experience. One influential answer to this question are theories of “basic emotions”, of which Ekman (1994a) is a leading proponent. Referring to Darwin (1890), these theories describe emotions as a set of 4 to 12 fundamental emotions shared by all humans but also apes and other animals and characterized by innate, pre-wired eliciting conditions, bodily arousal, facial expressions and behavioral responses. The extent to which the available data vindicates these views has been hotly debated (Russell, 1994; Ekman, 1994b; Russell, 1995) and the number of basic emotions also varies between authors and theories. Usually, most of them are negative emotions such as fear and anger, which are not necessarily the most relevant feelings for designers. Another influential approach thinks of emotions in terms of broad underlying dimensions such as valence and arousal or positive affect and negative affect (Yik, Russell, & Feldman Barrett, 1999), forming a kind of “minimal universality” (Russell, 1995). Beyond this “core affect” (Russell, 2003) or basic approach/avoidance

systems (Watson, Wiese, Vaidya, & Tellegen, 1999), culture, gender, personality and other individual differences shape the personal experience in profoundly different ways.

These dimensional approaches form the basis of many emotion measurement tools, including the feelings questionnaires described in this paper.

• Review of available self-report tools

Most research on emotions involved some form of self-report, asking participants in a study to report their feelings in a more or less formal way, from open-ended verbalizations to psychometric scales and questionnaires. Among the latter type of instruments, a handful of tools enjoy a wide use and therefore function as standards for the field. We will mention here three verbal tools, two widely used questionnaires and a newer one, and two graphical self-report tools, one generic and one design-oriented.

Among the dimensional approaches described above PAD (Pleasure – Arousal – Dominance) is an influential framework. This three-dimensional structure has been found in many types of data, including self-report of affect and analysis of affective vocabulary. It can be traced as far back as Wilhelm Wundt. Osgood, Suci & Tannenbaum (1957) provided an influential formulation of this model. Russell & Mehrabian (1974) describe a set of bipolar scales to collect self-report based on this model. They consist of 18 pairs of adjective such as “cheerful-melancholic” or “wild-lazy” and the participants have to indicate from which of these adjectives their present feelings are the closest. Besides the original English version, Mehrabian provides a German translation. We could also locate a validation of a Spanish version (Soriano & Foxall, 2002). A partial Dutch version has also been used in design-oriented sensory research (Schifferstein & Tanudjaja, 2004).

Another comparable questionnaire is the Positive Affect Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS, Watson, Clark & Tellegen, 1988). It provides a measure of positive and negative activation, conceived as two orthogonal – rather than one bipolar – dimensions (Tellegen, Watson, & Clark, 1999; Crawford, & Henry, 2004) but this structure can be at least imperfectly reconciled with the PAD or valence-arousal models of emotions (Yik, Russell, & Feldman Barrett, 1999; Tellegen, Watson & Clark, 1999; see also the answers in the same journal). The PANAS comprises twenty items, in the form of a list of adjectives such as “inspired”, “proud”, “hostile” or “scared”. For each adjective, participants have to rate how much they feel that way from 1 (“very slightly or not at all”) to 5 (“extremely”). The PANAS is widely used in clinical and health psychology but also in sport psychology (Crocker, 1997), mostly as measurement of mood or trait affect rather than as a measurement of feelings *per se* but it could find its use in design, for example to study the relationship between mood and product use. Many translations from this questionnaire have been developed and tested, including in Dutch (Peeters, Ponds & Vermeeren, 1996), French (Gaudreau, Sanchez & Blondin, 2006), German (Krohne, Egloff, Kohlmann & Tausch, 1996), Italian (Terracciano, McCrae & Costa, 2003), Japanese (Sato & Yasuda, 2001) and Polish (Brzozowski, 1991).

Unlike, the PAD scales and the PANAS, the Geneva Emotion Wheel (GEW) has not been developed as a psychometric measurement of a handful of dimensions but is based on a set of 20 emotion families. It also does not seem very widely used in psychology, being quite new (Scherer, 2005) but might be interesting to the designer as it attempts to provide a standard measurement of discrete emotions. These discrete emotions can sometimes be more telling to designers than broad dimensions.

To date, the developers of this questionnaire provide three versions (English, French and German). The second half of this paper is devoted to the development of a Dutch translation and its use in a design-related context.

Another class of tools that is especially interesting for intercultural research is graphical self-report instruments. Like questionnaires, they are based on a person's own ratings of his or her feelings but pictures (typically smiling or frowning faces) are used instead of words to anchor the scales. While this technique forgoes the need for translation and avoids a strong tie with a particular language, a graphical questionnaire still needs to be tested with different users as the interpretation and relevance of a graphical representation of feelings or dimensions of emotional experience might differ between cultures.

The most common of these graphical self-reports is probably the Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM, Bradley & Lang, 1994). Originally based on the PAD model, it is made of three scales, one for each of the dimensions valence, arousal and dominance, and has been shown to correlate highly with the original verbal scales. It enjoys wide use within several psychological disciplines and has been used to construct several sets of standard emotion-eliciting stimuli (e.g. Lang, Bradley, & Cuthbert, 2005). Dormann (2003) provides one example of use in design research. Another tool especially relevant for designers is PrEmo (Desmet, 2003). It has been developed specifically for design research, including a number of positive emotions usually neglected in psychological research. Between 10 and 14 animations representing a range of emotions are presented to the user, who should indicate if his or her feelings are close to the emotion represented by the animations. Using sound and movement allows for fine-grained distinctions between subtle emotions that are only partially accounted for in a dimensional tool like the SAM. Regarding cross-cultural use, the labels associated with each emotion have been checked with participants in the Netherlands, the US, Japan and Finland. The tool has also proved useful in a study of affective responses to automotive design in Japan and the Netherlands (Desmet, 2002).

Dutch translation of the Geneva Emotion Wheel

As mentioned above, the Geneva Emotion Wheel (GEW) is a relatively new self-report instrument for the measurement of feelings, the subjective, experiential component of emotions (Scherer, 2005). Unlike most standardized tools, it is not based on broad dimensions such as valence, arousal and dominance or positive and negative affect but on categorical or discrete emotions. The main issue with dimensional self-report tools is the difficulties in interpreting the meaning of the basic underlying dimensions. Specifically, "valence" ratings could refer to the perceived qualities of the eliciting object or to the feeling itself. Similarly, arousal can easily be confused with intensity. Also, a position in a two or three-dimensional emotion space is somewhat ambiguous, with considerable overlap between different emotion categories. For example anger and fear, both high arousal/low valence emotions, would produce similar scores with scales measuring only these two dimensions. Specific verbal labels, referring to particular discrete emotions, could allow for fine-grained differentiation and comparisons between individuals or between several emotional episodes experienced by one person.

Unfortunately, self-report instruments based on discrete emotions tend to be ad hoc questionnaires and adjective lists, harming the comparability between studies and the accumulation of knowledge in this field. The Geneva Emotion Wheel was developed to improve on this situation, by the design of a questionnaire going beyond the valence-arousal space but organizing verbal labels in a systematic fashion that would make the tool easier to use, and more reliable across studies (Scherer, 2005).

The current version of the Geneva Emotion Wheel consists of a set of 20 emotion families, selected among those most studied in the field or considered as "basic emotions". These emotion families are organized in a circle, but instead of grouping them according to the traditional valence and arousal dimensions, their position is determined by fundamental appraisal dimensions. The vertical axis represents the power/control appraisal and the horizontal axis the pleasantness/obstructiveness appraisal. The Geneva Emotion Research Group provides English, French and German-language versions of the Geneva Emotion Wheel. The current paper presents a translation of the questionnaire into Dutch and a preliminary validation study in a design research context. The first step was to develop a tentative translation of the various labels used in the Geneva Emotion Wheel. Table 1 shows the labels used in the study presented here, together with the original English-language version.

Table 1 – Translation of the emotion families of the Geneva Emotion Wheel

High control/Low pleasantness		High control/High pleasantness	
English	Dutch	English	Dutch
Irritation	Irritatie	Involvement	Betrokkenheid
Anger	Boosheid	Interest	Interesse
Contempt	Minachting	Amusement	Amusement
Scorn	Bitterheid	Laughter	Lachen
Disgust	Walging	Pride	Trots
Repulsion	Weerzin	Elation	Verrukking
Envy	Afgunst	Happiness	Geluk
Jealousy	Jalousie	Joy	Blijheid
Disappointment	Teleurstelling	Enjoyment	Genieten
Regret	Spijt	Pleasure	Plezier
Low control/Low pleasantness		Low control/High pleasantness	
English	Dutch	English	Dutch
Guilt	Schuld bewust	Tenderness	Genegenheid
Remorse	Berouw	Feeling love	Liefde voelen
Embarrassment	Gegeneerdheid	Wonderment	Verwondering
Shame	Schaamte	Feeling awe	Ontzag voelen
Worry	Verontrusting	Feeling disburdened	Bevrijd voelen
Fear	Angst	Relief	Opluchting
Sadness	Bedroefdheid	Astonishment	Verbazing
Despair	Vertwijfeling	Surprise	Varrassing
Pity	Medeleven	Longing	Verlangen
Compassion	Medeogen	Nostalgia	Nostalgie

To study the properties of the translation in a design context, we decided to compare ratings of two consumer products with the Geneva Emotion Wheel and PrEmo. This method provides a test of two aspects of construct validity (Cronbach & Meehl, 1955). Firstly, if the two instruments measure the same construct (emotion),

similarities between the ratings should be apparent in the data collected. Secondly, the measurement should conform to our theoretical understanding of product emotion, i.e. difference in affective response between both products should also be reflected in the results.

Method

The participants (N = 40) were asked to use two products and to report about their experience with both questionnaires after using each product. Participants (N = 40) were students in Industrial Design at the authors' institution, all of them native Dutch speakers. The products were chosen for their potential to elicit different emotions. One of them was a Phillips/Alessi designer coffee machine, the other one a rather complex alarm clock. As appraisal theories underline the importance of goals and concerns (Desmet & Hekkert, 2002) in affective responses, participants were asked to carry out a task with each product (brew coffee and set up an alarm).

Gebruik de bovenstaande schaalverdeling om jouw gevoel voor het product te beschrijven (meer dan een keuze mogelijk)

Emotie Intensiteitschaal:

Laag ● ● ● ● ● Hoog

Submit

Figure 1. Screenshot of the Dutch version of the Geneva Emotion Wheel as it was presented to the participants.

After using each product, the participants were asked to report their feelings using two questionnaires: the Dutch translation of the Geneva Emotion Wheel (GEW) presented above and PrEmo. Both questionnaires were administered on-screen. For each emotion family of the GEW, participants could indicate the level to which they experience the corresponding emotion on a five-point scale plus an implicit “not at all” position (see Figure 1). The version of PrEmo used here (see Figure 2) is a ten-emotions version similar to the one used in Desmet, Porcelijn & van Dijk (2005).

U kunt nu uw gevoel weergeven met de poppetjes. Gebruik de kleuren om aan te geven in welke mate de gevoelens uitgedrukt door ieder van de poppetjes overeenkomt met uw eigen gevoel.

(U kunt pas verder als u ELKE animatie een kleur heeft gegeven)

Ik voel dit STERK	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ik voel dit in ENIGE MATE	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ik voel dit NIET	<input type="checkbox"/>
Nog GEEN waarde geselecteerd:	<input type="checkbox"/>

Submit

Figure 2. Screenshot of PrEmo as it was presented to the participants.

The emotions included are positive surprise, satisfaction, fascination, amusement, desire, disgust, contempt, negative surprise, dissatisfaction and boredom. These labels correspond to the researcher's description of the emotions portrayed and were also validated in a study involving Japanese, US, Finnish and Dutch participants (Desmet, 2002) but they are not presented to the participants, who have to rate their experience based on the animations, without verbal description of the emotion. For each of the ten animations, participants had to indicate how closely it matched their feelings with a three-points scale ("Ik voel dit STERK" – I am feeling this strongly, "Ik voel dit in ENIGE MATE" – I am feeling this somewhat, "Ik voel dit NIET" – I do not feel like that).

To reduce spillover and learning effects, the order of products and questionnaire was counterbalanced. Half of the participants were asked to use the coffee machine first, while another half had to set up the alarm clock first. In each group, half of the participants used the Geneva Emotion Wheel first and the other half began to report their feelings with PrEmo.

Results

One common way to analyze the data collected in this study would be through some variants of factor analysis or principal components analysis. However, several indicators suggest that the data matrix is not appropriate for this type of analysis. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy is 0.475 for the alarm clock data and 0.352 for the coffee machine ratings, well beyond the acceptable limit of 0.5 or 0.6 and the matrix determinants are also

dangerously small (respectively 9.33E-13 and 8.32E-12). Consequently, the results of factor analyses are rather confused, with factors explaining little variance and many variables with low communalities. This is not altogether surprising given the fact that neither instruments is a psychometric questionnaire and that they were both intended to assess discrete emotions rather than underlying dimensions. The number of participants is also quite small for this type of analysis and the response format (3 and 5-points items) can attenuate the correlations and yield severe departure from normality. Instead of removing items to obtain an acceptable matrix and arbitrarily change the parameters of the model to find some meaningful structure, we therefore choose to look directly at the correlation matrix, which is still doable with 30 items (20 GEW emotion families and 10 PrEmo emotions) in total.

Figure 3. Correlation between emotion groups in both questionnaires for the alarm clock. Above the diagonal: τ coefficient. Text size is roughly proportional to the magnitude of the correlation. Stars represent the significance level: one star for $p < 0.05$, two stars for $p < 0.01$, three stars for $p < 0.001$. Below the diagonal: the size and color of the pie is proportional to the correlation.

The remaining of the discussion will use Kendall's τ as a correlation coefficient, as it is recommended as replacement for Pearson's r for non-normal data and small samples with a high number of ties.

Figure 4. Correlation between emotion groups in both questionnaires for the coffee machine. Above the diagonal: τ coefficient. Text size is roughly proportional to the magnitude of the correlation. Stars represent the significance level: one star for $p < 0.05$, two stars for $p < 0.01$, three stars for $p < 0.001$. Below the diagonal: the size and color of the pie is proportional to the correlation.

Based on a cursory observation of the data matrix, we decided to treat each quadrant of the Geneva Emotion Wheel (low or high control and low or high pleasantness) and each half of PrEmo (negative and positive emotions) as 6 scales, adding the ratings of all emotions in each group. While some of these groups of scores do not have the coherence usually expected from a psychometric scale, this strategy is also coherent with current theories of affect outlined in the literature review. Figure 3 and 4 show the resulting matrix and provide an overview of our findings.

For both products, PrEmo positive emotions show a moderate (negative) correlation with PrEmo negative emotions and with high control/low pleasantness emotions in the GEW. There are somewhat stronger correlations between PrEmo positive emotions and GEW positive emotions, both low and high control. GEW emotions with the same level of control or pleasantness are somewhat correlated, with the exception of low control emotions (positive and negative) for the coffee machine. There is also a significant negative correlation between high control emotions of opposite pleasantness. PrEmo negative emotions are strongly correlated with high control/low pleasantness emotions.

Emotion	Alarm clock		Coffee machine		Difference
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Positive surprise	0.73	0.716	1.28	0.751	- 0.550 ***
Satisfaction	0.68	0.616	1.25	0.670	- 0.575 ***
Fascination	0.38	0.628	0.95	0.677	- 0.575 ***
Amusement	0.43	0.675	0.50	0.599	- 0.075
Desire	0.48	0.716	0.70	0.687	- 0.225 *
Disgust	1.05	0.815	0.25	0.494	0.800 ***
Contempt	0.70	0.687	0.30	0.516	0.400 **
Negative surprise	0.70	0.751	0.40	0.672	0.100
Dissatisfaction	0.95	0.876	0.28	0.554	0.675 ***
Boredom	0.65	0.622	0.40	0.591	0.250 *
Involvement	1.45	1.694	2.08	1.730	- 0.625 *
Amusement	0.70	1.244	1.23	1.459	- 0.525
Pride	1.18	1.693	1.53	1.633	- 0.350
Happiness	0.45	1.037	1.15	1.477	- 0.700 **
Enjoyment	0.55	1.319	1.83	1.662	- 1.275 ***
Tenderness	0.10	0.379	0.33	0.944	- 0.225 *
Wonderment	0.40	0.955	1.35	1.594	- 0.950 ***
Relief	0.70	1.418	0.60	1.194	0.100
Astonishment	1.98	1.687	2.35	1.688	- 0.375
Longing	0.38	0.979	0.53	1.109	- 0.150
Pity	0.18	0.712	0.15	0.533	0.025
Sadness	0.85	1.331	0.05	0.221	0.800 ***
Worry	0.43	0.874	0.65	1.252	- 0.225
Shame	1.00	1.502	0.23	0.577	0.775 ***
Guilt	0.13	0.463	0.05	0.221	0.075
Regret	1.00	1.414	0.53	1.154	0.475
Envy	0.20	0.823	0.03	0.158	0.175
Disgust	1.18	1.500	0.28	0.784	0.900 ***

Scorn	1.30	1.471	0.48	0.987	0.825 ***
Irritation	2.85	1.733	0.33	0.797	2.525 ***

Stars represent the significance level (one star for $p < 0.05$, two stars for $p < 0.01$ and three stars for $p < 0.005$) in a paired T-Test with 39 degrees of freedom.

To test the relevance of these measurements for design-related research we tested the difference in mean rating for each emotion between the coffee machine and the alarm clock. If the tools compared here are able to measure product emotions, they should discriminate between the two products. As shown in table 2, many of these differences are significant, with the most important ones for “enjoyment” (GEW) and “irritation” (GEW). The emotions showing no significant difference between products are “amusement” (PrEmo), “negative surprise” (PrEmo), “pride” (GEW), “tenderness” (GEW), “relief” (GEW), “astonishment” (GEW), “longing” (GEW), “pity” (GEW), “worry” (GEW) and “envy” (GEW). Overall, both measurement tools show that the alarm clock elicit more negative and less positive emotions than the coffee machine.

Discussion

Overall, these results reflect the bipolar valence dimension usually thought to underlie emotions and show a great deal of correspondence between both instruments, supporting their convergent validity. Furthermore, the GEW low control/low pleasantness emotions (guilt, embarrassment, worry, sadness, pity) are absent from PrEmo.

The differences between products also support the construct validity of both questionnaires as product emotion measurements. The lack of noticeable difference in surprise-related emotions such as “negative surprise” (PrEmo) or “astonishment” (GEW) might be explained by the specific choice of products used in this study. The low difference in “amusement” is slightly more unexpected. Most other non-significant differences concern low control emotions, several of them (“pity”, “envy”, “pride”, “tenderness”) social emotions, typically associated with interpersonal relationships. While products can elicit this type of emotions (Desmet, & Hekkert, 2002), they are apparently less directly relevant to the products at hand.

Conclusions

The Dutch translation of the Geneva Emotion Wheel performs reasonably well and revealed a number of differences in affective experience with two products. However, until now it has only been tested in European cultures and there are reason to think that the control appraisal dimension is not so relevant for Asian cultures (Mesquita, 2005).

Further research is needed on this question.

PrEmo and the Geneva Emotion Wheel ratings are broadly similar and generally conform to what we know about emotions, supporting the construct validity of both tools. Depending on the needs of the researchers, they provide viable alternatives to assess feelings and test specific hypothesis on product experience.

References

- Bradley, M. M., & Lang, P. J. (1994). Measuring emotion: the Self-Assessment Manikin and the Semantic Differential. *Journal of Experimental Psychiatry & Behavior Therapy*, 25 (1), 49-59.
- Brzozowski, P. (1991). Internal structure stability of positive and negative concepts. *Polish Psychological Bulletin*, 22, 91–106.

- Crawford, J.R., & Henry, J.D. (2004). The Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS): Construct validity, measurement properties and normative data in a large non-clinical sample. *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 43 (3), pp. 245-265.
- Crocker, P.R.E. (1997). A confirmatory factor analysis of the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) with a youth sport sample. *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 19, 91-97.
- Darwin, C. (1890). *The expression of the emotions in man and animals*. London: J. Murray.
- Desmet, P.M.A. (2002). *Designing Emotions*. Phd Thesis, Delft University of Technology.
- Desmet, P.M.A. (2003). Measuring emotion; development and application of an instrument to measure emotional responses to products. In: M.A. Blythe, A.F. Monk, K. Overbeeke, & P.C. Wright (Eds.), *Funology: from usability to enjoyment* (pp. 111-123). Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Desmet, P.M.A., & Hekkert, P.P.M. (2002). The basis of product emotions. In W. Green & P. Jordan (Eds.), *Pleasure with Products, beyond usability* (pp. 60-68). London: Taylor & Francis.
- Desmet, P.M.A., Porcelijn, R., & van Dijk, M.B. (2005). HOW to design WOW?; Introducing a layered-emotional approach In: S. Wensveen (ed.), *Proceedings of The International Conference on Designing Pleasurable Products and Interfaces*, October 24-27, Eindhoven, pp. 71-89.
- Dormann, C. (2003). Affective experiences in the Home: measuring emotion. HOIT 2003.
- Ekman, P. (1994a). All Emotions Are Basic. In P. Ekman & R.J. Davidson (Eds.), *The Nature of emotion: Fundamental questions* (pp. 15-19). New York/Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Ekman, P. (1994b). Strong evidence for universals in facial expressions: A reply to Russell's mistaken critique. *Psychological Bulletin*, 115, 268-287.
- Ekman, P., & Oster, H. (1979). Facial Expression of Emotion. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 30, 527-554.
- Izard, C.E. (1977). *Human Emotions*. New York: Plenum Press.
- Gaudreau, P., Sanchez, X., & Blondin, J.-P. (2006). Positive and negative affective states in a performance-related setting testing the factorial structure of the PANAS across two samples of French-Canadian participants. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 22 (4), pp. 240-249.
- Krohne, H.W., Egloff, B., Kohlmann, C.-W., & Tausch, A. (1996). Investigations with a German version of the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS). *Diagnostica*, 42 (2), pp. 139-156.
- Lang, P.J., Bradley, M.M., & Cuthbert, B.N. (2005). *International affective picture system (IAPS): Digitized photographs, instruction manual and affective ratings*. Technical Report A-6. University of Florida, Gainesville, FL.
- Lutz, C., & White, G.M. (1986). The Anthropology of Emotions. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 15, 406-436.
- Mehrabian, A. (1995). Framework for a comprehensive description and measurement of emotional states. *Genetic, Social, and General Psychology Monographs*, 121, 339-361.
- Mehrabian, A., & Russell, J. A. (1974). *An approach to environmental psychology*. Cambridge: M.I.T. Press.
- Mesquita, B. (2005). Emotions are culturally situated. *Social Science Information*, 46 (3), 410-415.
- Osgood, C.E., Suci, G., & Tannenbaum, P. (1957). *The measurement of meaning*. Urbana, IL: University of Illinois Press.

- Peeters, F.P.M.L., Ponds, R.W.H.M., & Vermeeren, M.T.G. (1996). Affectivity and self-report of depression and anxiety. *Tijdschrift voor Psychiatrie*, 38 (3), pp. 240-250.
- Russell, J.A. (1994). Is there universal recognition of emotion from facial expression? A review of cross-cultural studies. *Psychological Bulletin*, 115, 102-141.
- Russell, J. A. (1995). Facial Expressions of Emotion: What Lies Beyond Minimal Universality? *Psychological Bulletin*, 118 (3), 379-391.
- Russell, J.A. (2003). Core Affect and the Psychological Construction of Emotion. *Psychological Review*, 110 (1), pp. 145-172.
- Scherer, K.R. (2005). What are emotions? And how can they be measured? *Social Science Information*, 44 (4), 693-727.
- Scherer, K.R., & Wallbott, H.G. (1994). Evidence for Universality and Cultural Variation of Differential Emotion Response Patterning. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 66 (2), 310-328.
- Schiffstein, H.N.J., & Tanudjaja, I. (2004). Visualising fragrances through colours: The mediating role of emotions. *Perception*, 33 (10), 1249-1266.
- Soriano, M.Y., & Foxall, G.R. (2002). A Spanish translation of Mehrabian and Russell's emotionality scales for environmental consumer psychology. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 2 (1), 23-36.
- Terraciano, A., McCrae, R.R., Costa, P.T. (2003). Factorial and construct validity of the Italian Positive and Negative Affect Schedule. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 19, 131-141.
- Tellegen, A., Watson, D., & Clark, L. A. (1999). On the Dimensional and Hierarchical Structure of Affect. *Psychological Science*, 10 (4), 297-303.
- Sato, A., & Yasuda, A. (2001). Development of the Japanese version of Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) scales. *Japanese Journal of Personality*, 10, pp. 15-26.
- Watson, D., Clark, L.A., & Tellegen, A. (1988). Development and validation of brief measures of positive and negative affect: the PANAS scales. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 54 (6), 1063-1070.
- Watson, D., Wiese, D., Vaidya, J., & Tellegen, A. (1999). The Two General Activation Systems of Affect: Structural Findings, Evolutionary Considerations, and Psychobiological Evidence. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 76 (5), 820-838.
- Yik, M.S.M., Russell, J.A., & Feldman Barrett, L. (1999). Structure of Self-Reported Current Affect: Integration and Beyond. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 77 (3), 600-619.